

Dynamic analysis of plates with thick unconstrained layer damping

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Abstract

In this work the dynamic behaviour of free layer damping plates with thick unconstrained viscoelastic layer is analysed. With this aim, the Kirchhoff–Love thin plate formulation is adapted to take shear stiffness into account by using a frequency dependent equivalent flexural stiffness.

To check the validity of the proposed formulation, it is implemented in a finite element model and compared to both the Oberst model and a reference 3D solid model in terms of eigenvalues and dynamic response across a wide range of boundary conditions — clamped in all edges, free, simply supported at edges, clamped in a single edge and simply supported at corners. In all the cases the material of the viscoelastic layer presents fractional damping, its modulus thus being complex and frequency dependent.

The results show that the proposed model is in good agreement with the 3D model and that it provides better accuracy than the Oberst model, specially as the thickness of the damping layer, and consequently the effect of the shear, increases. Hence, the need of developing a 3D solid model can be avoided as well as the storage and computation time problems it arises, that are specially critical in industrial practical applications.

Keywords: plate models, free layer damping, vibration reduction, fractional damping, finite element

1. Introduction

Free layer damping (FLD) plates are widely used to provide structural damping to structures subjected to vibration. FLD are formed by a base layer, in general metallic, coated by a layer of viscoelastic material, either in the form of damping tiles that are glued to the surface of interest [1] or surface treatments [2]. Its main application fields are human transportation systems [3, 4], appliances and buildings, mostly aiming to prevent structure-borne noise [5].

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In order to analyse the dynamic behaviour of such structures, several approaches can be followed, ranging from analytical to numerical. Analytical solutions are only useful when boundary conditions, structure shapes or damping models are simple; when any of them is complex, the natural choice is finite element modelling (FEM): either 2D or 3D models can be used to this aim.

Regarding two-dimensional models, the discretisation is performed with plate elements presenting an equivalent flexural stiffness that considers the properties of both the base and the viscoelastic layers. Even if most of this type of studies focus on unidimensional beams [6], the widely used Oberst model follows this approach [7]. More recently, a cantilever FLD plate has been modelled as a thin plate so that the effect of frequency dependence on the response could be analysed [8]. These homogenised models simplify the modelling process and allow for fast computation of the desired output. However, as the effect of the shear stress is neglected, they can only be used for thin plates, where the effect of shear stress is minimum.

In [9], triangular and rectangular sandwich elements with seven degrees of freedom in each node are proposed in order to describe the vibroacoustic behaviour of laminated steels. The drawback of this approach is the need to develop a specific model.

Conversely, 3D models provide a better representation of the behaviour of the plate but at a much higher computational cost [10], specially because a fine mesh or quadratic elements are required for results to be reliable. Storage requirements are more demanding as well.

Taking the former into account, in this work a new formulation for the equivalent flexural stiffness that considers the effect of the shear stress is proposed. Such an approach preserves the ease of modellisation and low computational time that a 2D model allows without a loss in precision. In addition, standard thin plate elements are used avoiding the need of developing a specific model.

This paper is organised as follows. First the formulation is described. Then, its implementation in a finite element simulation is presented, in which a fractional damping model is used to represent the frequency dependence of the damping properties of the viscoelastic layer. The proposed formulation is then compared to the Oberst method and to 3D solids in terms of natural frequencies, modal loss factor and dynamic response.

2. Formulation of a frequency dependent equivalent flexural stiffness for thick FLD plates

A FLD plate of size $A \times B$ formed by a base layer of thickness H_1 , elastic modulus E_1 , density ρ_1 and Poisson's modulus ν_1 , and a viscoelastic layer of thickness H_2 , elastic modulus E_2 , density ρ_2 and Poisson's modulus ν_2 is considered (Figure 1).

The proposed model extends the formulation developed by the authors for thick beams [11] to thick plates, following the example of [12] that extends Oberst's model from beams directly to plates. The objective is to deduce an

Figure 1: FLD plate

equivalent flexural stiffness that considers both materials and the effect of shear stress.

With this aim, first the equivalent flexural stiffness of the FLD plate is obtained, that, according to Oberst, is the sum of the flexural stiffnesses of the two layers

$$D_{\text{eq}} = D_1 + D_2, \quad (1)$$

D_1 and D_2 being the flexural stiffnesses of the base layer and the viscoelastic layer respectively.

Considering the limits of the two layers described in Figure 1, the equivalent flexural stiffness for the plate under study follows the expression

$$D_{\text{eq}} = \frac{E_1}{3(1-\nu_1^2)} \int_{-h_n}^{-h_n+H_1} z^2 dz + \frac{E_2}{3(1-\nu_2^2)} \int_{-h_n+H_1}^{-h_n+H_1+H_2} z^2 dz \quad (2)$$

where h_n stands for the height of the neutral plane and is given by

$$h_n = \frac{E_1 H_1^2 + E_2 H_2 (2H_1 + H_2)}{2(E_1 H_1 + E_2 H_2)}. \quad (3)$$

Following [11], the shear and bending behaviours are considered to be uncoupled, so the resistance to bending can be attributed to the flexural stiffness and the resistance to shear to the shear stiffness alone.

The shear stiffness of the plate is obtained by combining the shear stiffnesses of the two layers as

$$\frac{1}{K_{\text{eq}}} = \frac{1}{K_1} + \frac{1}{K_2}. \quad (4)$$

Taking into account the geometry of the plate under study and assuming a quadratic shear stress, K_1 and K_2 follow

$$\frac{1}{K_1} = \frac{1}{G_1 B_{\text{eq}}^2} \int_{-h_n}^{-h_n+H_1} \Omega_1^2 dz, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{K_2} = \frac{1}{G_2 B_{\text{eq}}^2} \int_{-h_n+H_1}^{-h_n+H_1+H_2} \Omega_2^2 dz, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\Omega_1 = \int_{-h_n}^z E_1 z dz = \frac{E_1 (h_n^2 - z^2)}{2}, \quad (7)$$

$$\Omega_2 = \int_{-h_n+H_1+H_2}^z E_1 z dz = \frac{E_2 (H_1 + H_2 - h_n)^2 - z^2}{2} \quad (8)$$

and

$$B_{\text{eq}} = E_1 I_1 + E_2 I_2. \quad (9)$$

Then, in analogy to [11], the frequency dependent flexural stiffness is defined as

$$D(\omega) = \frac{D_{\text{eq}}}{\left(\varphi(\omega) + \sqrt{\varphi(\omega)^2 + 1}\right)^2}, \quad (10)$$

where $\varphi(\omega)$ is given by

$$\varphi(\omega) = \frac{\omega \sqrt{D_{\text{eq}} \rho_S}}{2K_{\text{eq}}}, \quad (11)$$

$\rho_S = \rho_1 H_1 + \rho_2 H_2$ being the mass per unit area of the plate and D_{eq} and K_{eq} the equivalent flexural stiffness and shear stiffness from (2) and (4).

Finally, the proposed frequency dependent flexural stiffness $D(\omega)$ is introduced in the Kirchhoff–Love equation for thin plates, resulting in

$$D(\omega) \left(\frac{\partial^4 u(x, y, t)}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 u(x, y, t)}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 u(x, y, t)}{\partial y^4} \right) + \rho_s \frac{\partial^2 u(x, y, t)}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (12)$$

so that the effect of the shear stress is considered. Throughout this work the variable u is used to denote the transverse displacement of the plate instead of the most typical w so as to avoid confusion with the frequency ω .

It should be noted that, even if frequency dependence could be considered a drawback of the method, it does not introduce in general more complexity to the model as the damping models for the viscoelastic material in FLD applications are usually frequency dependent.

Also, if the modulus of the viscoelastic material is considered to be complex, the described formulation is still valid substituting the modulus E_2 for its complex counterpart E_2^* , that can be or not frequency dependent as well.

3. Dynamic analysis of a FLD plate using finite elements

In order to check the validity of the proposed formulation, it is implemented in a finite element model in MATLAB[®].

The plate under consideration has an area of $0.1 \text{ m} \times 0.1 \text{ m}$ and the base material has a thickness $H_1 = 2 \text{ mm}$. Three different values (2 mm, 6 mm, 10 mm) are selected for the thickness of the viscoelastic layer H_2 in order to test the formulation in a range covering thin and thick plates.

The properties of the materials are taken from the experimental characterisation of an AISI T 316L stainless steel laminated sheet and a Soundown Vibration Damping Tile material effectuated by Cortés and Elejabarrieta in [13].

The density of the steel layer is $\rho_1 = 7782 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and its Young's modulus is $E_1 = 176.24 \text{ GPa}$. The viscoelastic layer has a density of $\rho_2 = 1423 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and a complex elastic modulus that follows a four parameter fractional model, that can be expressed as

$$E_2^*(\omega) = \frac{E_0 + E_\infty (i\omega\tau)^\alpha}{1 + (i\omega\tau)^\alpha} \quad (13)$$

in the frequency domain, where E_0 and E_∞ are the relaxed and unrelaxed moduli respectively, τ is the relaxation time and α is the fractional parameter. The values of the parameters are collected in Table 1. For simplicity and without losing generality, a value of $\nu_1 = \nu_2 = 0.3$ was considered for both materials.

E_0 (GPa)	E_∞ (GPa)	τ (μs)	α
0.353	3.462	314.9	0.873

Table 1: Values of the parameters of the fractional model

Two different finite element models are used to study the dynamic behaviour of the plate: a two-dimensional and a three-dimensional one. In the first case, the domain is discretised with the four node plate elements shown in Figure 2 with three degrees of freedom in each node: the transverse displacement u and the rotations θ_x and θ_y . The elementary matrices for the element can be found in Appendix A.

Figure 2: Plate element

The second one is a 3D model based on quadratic hexaedra with 27 nodes and it is used as a reference to estimate the accuracy of both 2D models (see a book on finite elements for the details, e.g., [14]).

The plate model has 50 nodes in each direction and the quadratic 3D model has 10 nodes in each direction of the plate plane and 5 along the thickness. The mesh size ensures convergence for the first five modes for all the boundary conditions in both cases.

The simply supported cases are exceptional. As the boundary conditions are not easily applicable to a 3D model because of computational issues due to locality, a finer mesh of $20 \times 20 \times 5$ nodes is used.

Once the models are set up, the natural frequencies and modal loss factors and the dynamic response when the FLD plate is subjected to a uniform pressure are computed in order to check the validity of the proposed formulation.

3.1. Natural frequencies and modal loss factor

The eigenpairs of the system satisfy the relation

$$(-\lambda_r^* \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}^*(\omega_r)) \phi_r^* = \mathbf{0} \quad (14)$$

where $\omega_r = \text{Re}(\sqrt{\lambda_r^*})$ is the natural frequency for r -th mode and λ_r^* and ϕ_r^* are respectively the corresponding eigenvalue and eigenvector. In the case under study the eigenvalues are complex because the modulus of the viscoelastic material E_2^* is complex, which also implies that the stiffness matrix is also complex. As for the eigenvectors, the viscoelastic layer covers the whole plate, so the damping is proportional and, thus, the eigenvectors are real, i.e., the system presents normal modes [15]. In a general case, both eigenvalues and eigenvectors should be complex.

The complex stiffness matrix varies with frequency, so an iterative method must be used to compute the eigenpairs of the system. The computation starts considering the static stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}(0)$ in (14) and solving the resulting eigenvalue and eigenvector problem

$$(-\lambda_{r,0} \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}(0)) \phi_{r,0} = \mathbf{0} \quad (15)$$

from which the natural frequency $\omega_{r,0}$ is obtained taking into account that $\omega_{r,0} = \sqrt{\lambda_{r,0}}$.

Then, the stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}(\omega_{r,0})$ is computed and the eigenpairs are updated accordingly obtaining $\omega_{r,1}$. If the difference $|\omega_{r,1} - \omega_{r,0}|$ is less than a given tolerance, the computation stops; if not, the value $\omega_{r,1}$ is used to update the stiffness matrix again and the cycle is repeated now obtaining a new value $\omega_{r,2}$. The procedure continues until all the needed eigenpairs are obtained with the desired tolerance.

It should be noted that, because of its formulation, the proposed method implies that for a given frequency ω , the complex stiffness matrix can be computed from the static stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}(0)$ as

$$\mathbf{K}^*(\omega) = \frac{D^*(\omega)}{D(0)}\mathbf{K}(0) \quad (16)$$

which simplifies the computation process and allows to mesh in an external program, export the mass and stiffness matrices of the system and introduce the dependence to frequency simply by multiplying by the flexural stiffness defined in (10).

In this work, a maximum difference of 0.1 rad/s between two consecutive computed natural frequencies is set as stopping criterion, but the same results are obtained linking the stopping criterion to the loss factor and with the iterative procedure proposed in [16].

Eigenpairs are then computed for different boundary conditions: clamped in all edges, free, clamped in a single edge, simply supported in all edges and simply supported at corners. In every case the results given by the proposed method are closer to the reference 3D model than the ones by the Oberst method — the details will be discussed in sections 3.1.1 to 3.1.5.

Also, it should be remarked that the plate model reproduces accurately the results obtained for thick beams in [11], corroborating its coherence and its validity for small widths.

The results for the cases analysed are presented in the following sections. For all cases, natural frequency ω and loss factor η of the first three modes are shown, the ones that are significant for the acoustic response, where the loss factor is defined for the r -th mode as

$$\eta_r = \frac{\text{Im}(\lambda_r^*)}{\text{Re}(\lambda_r^*)}. \quad (17)$$

3.1.1. Clamped in all edges

The results for the clamped case for the three values of thickness are shown in Tables 2–4. For every case, due to the symmetry of the plate, the second mode is double.

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	10446	0.0489	21369	0.0287	31397	0.0208
Proposed model	10475	0.0495	21447	0.0294	31557	0.0214
Oberst model	10511	0.0499	21601	0.0297	31891	0.0218

Table 2: Modal properties of the clamped plate when $H_2=2$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	15130	0.1424	29643	0.0790	42138	0.0569
Proposed model	15739	0.1500	31039	0.0882	44043	0.0670
Oberst model	16609	0.1403	34397	0.7710	50885	0.0554

Table 3: Modal properties of the clamped plate when $H_2=6$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	20743	0.1354	37846	0.0792	51917	0.0590
Proposed model	22784	0.1489	41623	0.0986	56171	0.0813
Oberst model	26633	0.1136	54849	0.0616	81030	0.0441

Table 4: Modal properties of the clamped plate when $H_2=10$ mm

The results for natural frequencies show good agreement between the three models for the thinnest viscoelastic layer, with a maximum deviation from the reference 3D model of 1.6 % for the Oberst model and of 0.5 % for the proposed formulation. For the 6 mm layer results start to diverge: while the proposed formulation is able to compute the natural frequencies of the clamped FLD plate within a maximum error of 4.5 %, the Oberst model reaches a deviation of 21 %.

The discrepancy between the Oberst and the reference model increases even more at higher frequencies, where the effect of the shear stress is more significant, reaching for the third mode and the thickest viscoelastic layer an error of 56 % while the proposed model only deviates 8 % from the three-dimensional model.

The differences in the computed natural frequencies using the Oberst model and the proposed one derive from the expression of the equivalent flexural stiffness $D^*(\omega)$. As illustrated in Figure 3, the real part of $D^*(\omega)$, decays with frequency in order to take into account the effect of the shear.

Figure 3: Real and imaginary parts of the equivalent flexural stiffness $D^*(\omega)$ for the Oberst model and the proposed one. The tendency is common for all the cases, so just the one for $H_2 = 10$ mm is represented.

The loss factor shows bigger scatter, but, as natural frequencies for the three models are different, the values of modal loss factor η are not directly comparable [17]. This differences in modal loss factor arise from the dependence to frequency of both the real and imaginary parts of the flexural stiffness $D^*(\omega)$. The fact that the proposed model predicts a higher value of loss factor is related to its lower stiffness and thus higher damping [18].

3.1.2. Free

The results for the free case for the three values of thickness are shown in Tables 5–7. For every case, the rigid solid modes are ignored.

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	3816	0.0770	5651	0.0691	7049	0.0621
Proposed model	3832	0.0783	5640	0.0694	7021	0.0626
Oberst model	3936	0.0785	5650	0.0697	7038	0.0630

Table 5: Modal properties of the free plate when $H_2=2$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	5506	0.3027	8509	0.2314	10631	0.1954
Proposed model	5686	0.3083	8503	0.2365	10609	0.2018
Oberst model	5813	0.3018	8767	0.2285	11015	0.1931

Table 6: Modal properties of the free plate when $H_2=6$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	8443	0.2846	13036	0.2053	16022	0.1732
Proposed model	8926	0.2921	12960	0.2234	15894	0.1928
Oberst model	9555	0.2609	14229	0.1905	17778	0.1589

Table 7: Modal properties of the free plate when $H_2=10$ mm

The free case follows the same trends identified in the previous section. The natural frequencies being lower due to the boundary conditions, the effect of shear is not as critical and the proposed formulation only gives significantly better results for the thickest viscoelastic layer, where the error in natural frequency is reduced from 10 % to 0.8 % for the third mode.

In this case, the values of the modal loss factor for the three models fall in a narrower range because at lower frequencies the difference between Oberst's equivalent flexural stiffness and the proposed one is less acute.

3.1.3. Clamped in one edge

The results for the plate when it is clamped in one of its edges for the three values of thickness are shown in Tables 8–10.

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	953.1	0.0579	2384	0.0788	6210	0.0653
Proposed model	946.7	0.0579	2380	0.0802	6139	0.0668
Oberst model	947.0	0.0580	2382	0.0804	6151	0.0671

Table 8: Modal properties of the plate clamped in one edge when $H_2=2$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	1135	0.4364	3257	0.3800	9148	0.2120
Proposed model	1131	0.4406	3366	0.3902	9268	0.2199
Oberst model	1136	0.4418	3416	0.3868	9582	0.2119

Table 9: Modal properties of the plate clamped in one edge when $H_2=6$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	1804	0.6236	5027	0.3932	13381	0.1957
Proposed model	1818	0.6355	5472	0.3928	14033	0.2086
Oberst model	1860	0.6234	5736	0.3671	15512	0.1762

Table 10: Modal properties of the plate clamped in one edge when $H_2=10$ mm

For the plate when it is clamped in a single edge, similar results are obtained with the three model for the thinnest and medium viscoelastic layers. The differences grow with both the thickness of the viscoelastic layer and the frequency, reaching a maximum divergence from the reference model of 16 % for the Oberst model for the third mode while the proposed model is able to stay within a 5 % of error.

The fact that for $H_2=2$ mm the results do not follow the general tendency can be attributed to the complete integration that stiffens too much the 3D model when the thickness is small.

3.1.4. Simply supported in all edges

For the simply supported cases, in order to accurately reproduce the boundary conditions using solid elements, displacement in the three directions is restricted along the medium line.

In reality, the transverse section rotates around the neutral axis but, as its position varies with frequency, it implies that the boundary conditions should be modified depending on the frequencies of the mode that is being computed. Given the thickness of the plate, setting the boundary conditions at the middle does not introduce much error and simplifies the implementation.

Another issue related with the 3D model is that applying the boundary condition in a single line creates local problems, specially at higher frequencies, that are completely avoided if the domain is discretised using plate elements instead of solids.

The modal properties for the simply supported case can be found in Tables 11–13. The second mode is double also in this case.

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	5659	0.0688	14462	0.0387	23053	0.0269
Proposed model	5681	0.0692	14408	0.0397	23063	0.0277
Oberst model	5691	0.0695	14477	0.0401	23242	0.0281

Table 11: Modal properties of the simply supported plate when $H_2=2$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	8286	0.2351	20853	0.1103	32088	0.0750
Proposed model	8565	0.2353	21283	0.1182	33182	0.0837
Oberst model	8836	0.2273	22976	0.1079	37027	0.0725

Table 12: Modal properties of the simply supported plate when $H_2=6$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	12207	0.2199	28364	0.1049	41422	0.0744
Proposed model	13048	0.2223	30001	0.1229	44099	0.0949
Oberst model	14334	0.1893	36725	0.0867	59023	0.0578

Table 13: Modal properties of the simply supported plate when $H_2=10$ mm

In this case, the three models do not differ excessively for the thinnest viscoelastic layer (less than 1 %) but the differences grow for the medium thickness, reaching a 15 % for the Oberst model while the proposed model stays within a 3.4 % maximum deviation and a 29 % and a 5.8 % for the thickest viscoelastic layer. In all the cases the greatest divergence is found for the third mode.

As for the modal loss factor, it is higher for the proposed model because the imaginary part of flexural stiffness $D^*(\omega)$ decays faster than its real part.

3.1.5. Simply supported at corners

Following the criterion for the simply supported plate, the boundary conditions in the 3D model were applied in the middle of the vertical edge at corners.

The results for this case are gathered in Tables 14–16.

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	1963	0.0763	4440	0.0725	5633	0.0696
Proposed model	1978	0.0781	4510	0.0753	5640	0.0696
Oberst model	1979	0.0779	4517	0.0750	5650	0.0693

Table 14: Modal properties of the plate simply supported at corners when $H_2=2$ mm

Also in this case the general trend is followed, the 3D model being the one with the lowest value of natural frequency for each mode and the Oberst one presenting the highest. Still, the results for the three models are highly divergent reaching a maximum difference of 33 % for the Oberst model and a 23 % for the proposed formulation for the third mode and thickest viscoelastic layer. These

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	2590	0.4172	6190	0.2649	8503	0.2325
Proposed model	2719	0.4196	6752	0.2715	8503	0.2333
Oberst model	2752	0.4175	6926	0.2646	8770	0.2256

Table 15: Modal properties of the plate simply supported at corners when $H_2=6$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	3860	0.4502	8520	0.2545	13043	0.2060
Proposed model	4468	0.4419	10469	0.2564	12960	0.2207
Oberst model	4654	0.4182	11315	0.2257	14229	0.1888

Table 16: Modal properties of the plate simply supported at corners when $H_2=10$ mm

high deviations can be attributed to the modelling of the boundary conditions in the three dimensional model that do not restrict the structure enough and illustrate why meshing a plate with 3D solids is not advisable.

3.2. Dynamic response

Then, the response of the plate is computed. Given a frequency value ω the complex response vector \mathbf{u}^* can be obtained by solving

$$(-\omega^2 \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}^*(\omega)) \mathbf{u}^* = \mathbf{F}(\omega) \quad (18)$$

where the force vector $\mathbf{F}(\omega)$ is in this case a uniform pressure on the surface of the plate (1 Pa) represented by the Heaviside function in the frequency domain. For the numerical application, a frequency range between 0 and 10 kHz is chosen, considering 600 samples in between so that the resolution is acceptable. The upper limit is set at 10 kHz because higher frequencies are not relevant for the acoustic response.

For the comparison between models, the RMS value of the transverse response $u(\omega)$ on the plate surface is used. For each frequency ω this value is obtained as

$$u_{\text{rms}}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |u_N(\omega)|^2} \quad (19)$$

where N is the number of nodes in the model.

Results for different boundary conditions are presented in sections 3.2.1 to 3.2.4. All the plots show the dynamic amplification, i.e., the amplitude of the dynamic response divided by the static response.

Some general trends can be identified across all cases:

- The amplitude of the response is similar for the three models, the location of the resonant peak being different.

- The differences between the response curves increase with the thickness of the viscoelastic layer.
- Increasing the thickness of the viscoelastic layer brings a reduction in the amplitude of the response.
- For the thickest viscoelastic layer the Oberst model is unable to represent correctly the response of the plate, specially at high frequencies.
- For the whole frequency range and the three values of thickness the proposed model is able to produce a response curve close to the reference.

3.2.1. Clamped in all edges

Figure 4 shows the dynamic amplification for the clamped plate for the three different thickness values. The three models reach similar amplitudes across the whole frequency range the main difference being the frequency of the resonant peak. In this case, if the Oberst model is used, it could seem that the response at 8 kHz is inexistent, but, actually, a resonant peak is being excited.

Figure 4: Dynamic amplification for the clamped case: (a) $H_2=2$ mm; (b) $H_2=6$ mm; (c) $H_2=10$ mm

3.2.2. Clamped in one edge

The dynamic amplification curves for the three values of the viscoelastic layer when the plate is clamped in a single edge are gathered in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Dynamic amplification when the plate is clamped in a single edge: (a) $H_2=2$ mm; (b) $H_2=6$ mm; (c) $H_2=10$ mm

The response curve for the thinnest viscoelastic layer shows the same effect that was described in Section 3.1.3 when comparing the natural frequencies given by the three models: the 3D model is too stiff for high frequencies and the response curve is displaced to the right.

For the rest, the general trends are observed: the two plate models are in good agreement when the thickness of the viscoelastic layer is small and the differences with the three dimensional model are increased with the thickness, the amplitude of the response being similar for the three cases.

3.2.3. Simply supported in all edges

In Figure 6 the dynamic amplification for the simply supported case is shown. Even if the 3D model presents the locality problems stated when comparing the eigenvalues, the computed response is nearly identical for the first two resonant peaks when $H_2 = 2$ mm and for the first peak when $H_2 = 6$ mm. The main

differences can be seen for the thickest viscoelastic layer, for which the Oberst model misses again the peak located at 8 kHz.

Figure 6: Dynamic amplification for the simply supported: (a) $H_2=2$ mm; (b) $H_2=6$ mm; (c) $H_2=10$ mm

3.2.4. Simply supported at corners

Figure 7 shows the dynamic amplification of the plate when it is supported at its corners. In this case, even if the general trends are followed, the differences between the three models for the thickest viscoelastic layer are greater. As said when analysing the eigenvalues, the reason of this divergence is the modelling of the boundary conditions in the three dimensional model that do not restrict enough the movement of the plate.

4. Conclusions

A new formulation for free layer damping plates with thick unconstrained damping layer is proposed and implemented in a finite element model in order to compare it to the well known Oberst model and a 3D model for reference.

The natural frequency, modal loss factor and dynamic response are computed for a wide range of boundary conditions, the results for the proposed formulation

Figure 7: Dynamic amplification when the plate is simply supported at its four corners: (a) $H_2=2$ mm; (b) $H_2=6$ mm; (c) $H_2=10$ mm

being specially accurate for thick damping layers, where the effect of shear stress is not negligible.

The formulation show similar degree of accuracy as the 3D model but presents several advantages over it. The first is the reduction in computational time derived from a model of a more limited size.

Besides, as the frequency dependence lies outside the stiffness matrix, the proposed model allows to mesh the structure under study in an external program, export system matrices \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} and introduce the frequency dependence by multiplying the stiffness matrix by a complex flexural stiffness $D^*(\omega)$ in order to compute the desired output. In addition, this approach overcomes the impossibility to implement complex damping formulations that commercial software shows.

Finally, boundary conditions are easier to apply, represent better the behaviour of the structure and avoid spurious modes due to locality. This is specially the case for simply supported boundary conditions, that are difficult to implement in 3D models.

Frequency dependence, that could be considered a weakness of the formulation, is diluted by the fact that damping models for the viscoelastic material

$$\begin{aligned}
f_8 &= a^2 + 10b^2 - a^2\nu \\
f_9 &= 5a^2 - 2b^2 + 2b^2\nu \\
f_{10} &= a^2 - 10b^2 - a^2\nu \\
f_{11} &= -5a^4 - 5b^4 + 7a^2b^2 - 2a^2b^2\nu \\
f_{12} &= 5a^2 - b^2 + b^2\nu \\
f_{13} &= -a^2 + 5b^2 + a^2\nu \\
f_{14} &= -10a^4 + 5b^4 - 7a^2b^2 + 2a^2b^2\nu \\
f_{15} &= 10a^2 - b^2\nu + b^2 \\
f_{16} &= a^2 - 5b^2 + 4a^2\nu \\
f_{17} &= 5a^2 - b^2 + b^2\nu \\
f_{18} &= 10a^2 - b^2 + b^2\nu \\
f_{19} &= -2a^2 + 5b^2 + 2a^2\nu
\end{aligned}$$

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